

Development of a Quantum Mechanical Autoencoder Model

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Abstract. An auto encoder is a type of artificial neural network, which efficiently learns to replicate a set of data values. These values are unlabeled, so that the learning process is effectively unsupervised. The auto encoder is modelled by an encoding-decoding scheme, along with the option of internal compression. Data compression is a useful tool for simplifying distribution detail, so it can assist the auto encoder in optimizing a more vague representation of the learned distributions. Some amount of internal compression can be necessary to efficiently learn a set of data values.

Advantages in machine learning have recently (2018) been investigated in quantum mechanical qubit systems by [Havlíček et al.] among others. In continuation of their research, another group [Abbas et al.] formulated two definite feature maps to formulate an effective quantum neural network. One an input feature map $\mathcal{U}(\vec{x})$ depending on an input vector $\vec{x} \in \mathbb{R}^s$ of a circuit of s qubits. The other, a variational map $\mathcal{G}(\vec{\theta})$ depending on parameters $\vec{\theta}$, which may be varied. With these building blocks and a method of internal circuit compression formulated by [Romero et al.], my bachelor project sought to mathematically engineer and simulate a quantum mechanical autoencoder model. A definite model of this type has previously not been available, and this project introduces and tests a quantum circuit which has the properties of the classical auto encoder model. The tested model is given by a consecutive use of feature maps:

$$\mathcal{M}^\dagger(\vec{x}) \cdot \mathcal{G}^\dagger(\vec{\theta}_D) \cdot \hat{B} \cdot \mathcal{G}(\vec{\theta}_E) \cdot \mathcal{U}(\vec{x})|0\rangle^{\otimes s} \quad (1)$$

As the circuit size s and network depth d increases, the number of singular quantum logic gates scales by the polynomial $2s^2 + (2d + 5)s$. Internal compression is acquired by measuring a set of qubits (\hat{C}) and instantly replacing them by the $|0\rangle$ basis state (\hat{R}). This procedure is referred to as a bottleneck $\hat{B} = \hat{R} \cdot \hat{C}$. The feature map $\mathcal{M}(\vec{x})$ is applied last and acts as a mimic to the input feature map \mathcal{U} . The mimic \mathcal{M} is formulated so that the input vector \vec{x} can be reconstructed by the circuit state $\mathcal{M}(\vec{x})|0\rangle^{\otimes s}$. Specifically, the map is defined by a set of separable qubits $|x_i\rangle = R_y(x_i)\hat{H}|0\rangle$ for each $x_i \in \vec{x}$. Here R_y is the y -rotation matrix and \hat{H} is the Hadamard gate. The input vector can be reconstructed by repeated measurements of the qubits, with the formula

$$x_i = 2 \arctan(\sqrt{\Gamma_i}) - \frac{\pi}{2} \quad (2)$$

Where $\Gamma_i = |\alpha_i|^2/|\beta_i|^2$ is defined to be the qubit ratio probability of a general qubit $|\psi\rangle = \alpha|0\rangle + \beta|1\rangle$. The circuit of the quantum mechanical auto encoder is simulated using the QuTiP python package.

A relatively large fidelity measure was acquired with the developed model, through testing on the Iris data set; A mean fidelity topping at 97.57% for an QAE model with a depth of 4 and compression 1. The Fisher information spectrum has been calculated for QAE models of varying amount of compression. The spectrum has considerably more large Fisher eigenvalues than that simulated by [Karakida et al.] on a classical auto encoder model. Graphs of training processes, input reconstruction and Fisher eigenvalues has been also constructed.

1. Introduction

This paper seeks to formulate and simulate a quantum mechanical autoencoder model, as an extension of the neural networks developed by Abbas et al. and Havlíček et al.. The developed QAE model is formulated from the ordinary encoding-bottleneck-decoding scheme. In addition, further advancements has been made to decode the reconstructed input features from the QAE circuit output.

The bottleneck operation has been formulated by Romero et al.. Based on their formulation, this paper seek to derive an expression for the state of a qubit circuit which has had the bottleneck applied to it.

A qubit circuit consists of a number s of qubit wires. Each wire can be labelled by an index i in an index set $I_s = \{i \in \mathcal{N} | 1 \leq i \leq s\}$. This paper denotes a general qubit circuit $|\Psi\rangle$ as the superposition of 2^s number of basis states. Each basis state can be labelled by $|\ell\rangle$, where ℓ is a subset of I_s .

$$|\Psi\rangle = \sum_{\ell \subseteq I_s} \phi_\ell |\ell\rangle \quad (3)$$

The collapse coefficients are normalized so that

$$\sum_{\ell \subseteq I_s} |\phi_\ell|^2 = 1 \quad (4)$$

2. Quantum neural networks

2.1. Kernels - Functional qubit circuits

The article by [Havlíček et al.] has opened the possibility of using quantum computing to simulate machine learning algorithms. They have shown experimental functionally on superconducting processors for specific gate combinations of CNOT and single qubit rotation gates. They are able to experimentally minimize a loss function by continually tuning training parameters $\vec{\theta}$, which are encoded in the physical qubit circuit. The changing circuit output as a function of a set of tunable parameters is called a kernel function by [Havlíček et al.]. A representation of a kernel function of a single qubit state is given in figure 1.

Figure 1. Depiction of a kernel function on the Bloch sphere. A kernel function of a single qubit $|\psi\rangle$ can be represented by an arbitrary closed loop on the unit Bloch sphere. The loop can be parametrized by two angular functions $\theta(\vec{\theta})$ and $\varphi(\vec{\theta})$.

2.2. Input feature and variational map

The input feature map is a unitary matrix $\mathcal{U}(\vec{x})$ which is applied onto a qubit circuit. [Abbas et al.]'s input map initiates with a Hadamard logic gate along with a Z-rotation matrix, applied on each qubit.

$$\mathcal{U}_I : |0\rangle_i \mapsto R_z(x_i) \hat{H} |0\rangle_i \quad (5)$$

We will note \mathcal{U}_I as the initial input feature map of \mathcal{U} . The initial encoding is further followed by an entangling map which consists of systematic use of a specific gate combination. It is sketched in figure 2.

It consists of the CNOT, $R_z(x_i, x_j)$ and CNOT gates applied in sequence. The two-variable rotation matrix is defined by a specific angular function $\phi(x_i, x_j) = (x_i - \pi)(x_j - \pi)$ in the regular rotation matrix: $R_z(x_i, x_j) \equiv R_z(\phi(x_i, x_j))$.

The variational map $\mathcal{G}(\vec{\theta})$ make a quantum circuit into a kernel function as it is applied onto it. By controllably varying the training parameters $\vec{\theta} \in \mathbb{R}^{2s(d+1)}$, the qubit circuit output may be varied accordingly. Like the classical neural network, the variational map is layered with a set of parameters associated with

Figure 2. Depiction of the quantum circuit studied by both [Havlíček et al.] and [Abbas et al.]. Two qubits $|\psi_i\rangle$ and $|\psi_j\rangle$ in a quantum circuit are applied a CNOT gate, a rotation matrix R_z and a CNOT gate. After the initial input feature map has been applied, this gate combination is applied iteratively on qubits $|\psi_i\rangle$ for each $i \in I_s$, and for all control qubits $|\psi_j\rangle$ above $|\psi_i\rangle$ in the circuit. Concretely, this gate combination is applied on target-control qubit pairs $|\psi_i\rangle$ and $|\psi_j\rangle$ for all $j > i$, for each $i \in I_s$. In all, a number of $\frac{s(s-1)}{2}$ of these gate combinations are applied in this process. The elaborate entanglement of the input feature vector into the circuit is an attempt to make the encoding difficult for a classical computer to simulate, so that it enforces an advantage for quantum computation (Havlíček et al., pg. 2).

each layer. For each layer, a y -rotation matrix $R_y(\theta_i)$ with training parameter θ_i is added to each qubit. Afterwards CNOT-gates are applied on target-control qubit pairs $|\psi_i\rangle$ and $|\psi_j\rangle$, for each $i \in I$ with $j > i$. This deployment is exactly the same as the one described in figure 2, but this time instead with singular CNOT-gates. The number of times this process is repeated, defines the depth d of the variational map.

3. Quantum mechanical auto encoder

3.1. Approach - Separability of qubit circuits

Consider the expression of a general two-level quantum mechanical system, namely a qubit:

$$|\psi\rangle = \alpha|0\rangle + \beta|1\rangle, \quad (\alpha, \beta) \in \mathbb{C}^2 \quad (6)$$

Upon measurement the qubit collapses into either of the basis states with probability $|\alpha|^2$ for one and $|\beta|^2$ for the other. The coefficients are normalized: $|\alpha|^2 + |\beta|^2 = 1$. This paper defines the **qubit probability ratio** as

$$\Gamma = \frac{|\alpha|^2}{|\beta|^2} = \frac{1}{|\beta|^2} - 1 \quad (7)$$

A feature $x \in [0; 1]$ can be encoded into this value so that Γ is a well-defined function of x . To extract the value from a qubit circuit, the circuit needs to be separable. Separability means a quantum system which is not entangled.

$$|\Psi\rangle = \bigotimes_{i \in I_s} |\psi_i\rangle \quad (8)$$

(separable qubit circuits)

The separable qubit circuit has the property, that an individual qubit's collapse probability can be calculated from the collapse probabilities of the entire qubit circuit:

$$|\beta_i|^2 = \sum_{\ell \subseteq I_s - \{i\}} |\phi_\ell|^2 \quad (9)$$

(separable qubit circuits)

The qubit probability ratio Γ_i of an individual qubit $|\psi\rangle_i$ can afterwards be calculated with equation (7).

3.2. Bloch sphere encoding - Feature encoding and reconstruction

Every unitary matrix can be decomposed into a sequence of Z-Y rotation matrices (Nielsen and Chuang, pg. 175). A special case of the decomposition describes the state of a qubit:

$$|\psi\rangle = e^{i\varphi} R_z(2\varphi) R_y(2\theta) H|0\rangle, \quad (10)$$

Calculating the expression yields a qubit on the surface of the Bloch sphere:

$$\sqrt{2}|\psi\rangle = (\cos\theta - \sin\theta)|0\rangle + e^{i\varphi}(\cos\theta + \sin\theta)|1\rangle \quad (11)$$

This qubit has a probability ratio equal to

$$\Gamma = \frac{1 + 2\cos\theta\sin\theta}{1 - 2\cos\theta\sin\theta} = \tan^2\left(\theta + \frac{\pi}{4}\right) \quad (12)$$

The qubit probability ratio is independent of the phase φ , so it is not needed in the gate construction in equation (10). We choose $\varphi = 0$. The elements of a feature vector $\vec{x} \in \mathbb{R}^s$ can be encoded into a qubit circuit of s qubits. Especially each feature x_i can be encoded into a qubit state $|x_i\rangle$ given by the gate construction

$$|x_i\rangle = R_y(x_i)H|0\rangle \quad (13)$$

θ was substituted for $x/2$ in equation (10). The feature x_i can be reconstructed given the corresponding qubit probability ratio Γ_i .

$$\Gamma_i = \tan^2\left(\frac{x_i}{2} + \frac{\pi}{4}\right) \quad (14)$$

$$\Rightarrow x_i = 2 \arctan \sqrt{\Gamma_i} - \frac{\pi}{2} \quad (15)$$

It would therefore be possible to encode the input feature vector \vec{x} into a separable qubit circuit consisting of Bloch sphere surface qubits. The quantum mechanical auto encoder should train to mimic this separable qubit circuit. After sufficient training, it will be possible to extract a reconstruction \vec{y} which is similar to the input feature vector. \vec{y} is calculated from the collapse probabilities of the auto encoder circuit, by using equation (9), (7) and (15) in that order.

3.3. The bottleneck - Internal circuit compression and dimensional restoration

The auto encoder model requires a sense of internal compression and dimensional restoration. These operations are labelled \hat{C} and \hat{R} respectively. The consecutive use of these operations is referred to as a **bottleneck**, $\hat{B} = \hat{R} \cdot \hat{C}$ (Bank et al., pg. 2). The bottleneck gives an option to apply varying dimensional reduction which is useful in the process of training the auto encoder as it counteracts overfitting (Bank et al., pg. 2).

In 2016 it was suggested by [Romero et al.] to measure a number of qubits in a qubit circuit to imitate the effect of internal compression of an auto encoder. The index set $I_c \subseteq I_s$ is noted as the set of circuit indices that label the qubits which have been measured after applying the compression operator \hat{C} . The amount of internal compression $c \leq s$ corresponds to the number of qubits internally measured. Instantly after compression, the measured qubits are replaced by the $|0\rangle$ basis state. This final operation \hat{R} restores dimensionality of the quantum circuit.

This paper makes a binary distinction of the measurement procedure. Either the internal measurements are recorded or they are not.

If the internal measurements are recorded then the circuit output is considered **non-deterministic**, since the qubit measurement collapses are probabilistic. For each subset ℓ_c of I_c there is a corresponding non-deterministic bottleneck operator $\hat{B}(\ell_c)$. Each is given by

$$\hat{B}(\ell_c) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\mathbb{P}(\ell_c)}} \sum_{\ell \subseteq I_s - I_c} |\ell\rangle \langle \ell \cup \ell_c|, \quad (16)$$

where $\mathbb{P}(\ell_c)$ is a factor of normalization. If the operator is applied onto a qubit circuit $|\Psi\rangle$, the factor is given by:

$$\mathbb{P}(\ell_c) = \sum_{\ell \subseteq I_s - I_c} |\phi_{\ell \cup \ell_c}|^2. \quad (17)$$

The probability that a given non-deterministic bottleneck operator $\hat{B}(\ell_c)$ is applied onto the qubit circuit is $\mathbb{P}(\ell_c)$. This operator has been derived from a couple of calculated examples made by (Nielsen and Chuang, pg. 18 and 88).

Since the measurement outcome is probabilistic it introduces ambiguity to the entire circuit output. There are 2^c distinct outcomes, which is not desirable for a neural network circuit. Consistency is key for the machine to learn.

Without loss of generality the *principle of implicit measurement* (Nielsen and Chuang, pg. 187) can be applied in reverse, so that a measured qubit can be assumed to be the termination of a quantum wire. The termination of a quantum wire enforces that the internal measurements are not recorded. The formulation of compression with a terminating wire instead of an active measurement will be considered as **deterministic** compression. With wire termination, the observer is fundamentally unaware of the measurement outcomes and the interference of all possible measurement outcomes is instead the total outcome of the bottleneck. The density matrix (Nielsen and Chuang, pg. 99) that describes the qubit circuit $|\Psi\rangle$ after deterministic compression is calculated as

$$\rho = \sum_{\ell_c \subseteq I_c} \mathbb{P}(\ell_c) \hat{B}(\ell_c) |\Psi\rangle \langle \Psi| \hat{B}^\dagger(\ell_c) \quad (18)$$

$$= \sum_{\ell \subseteq I_s - I_c} \mathbb{P}_\ell |\ell\rangle \langle \ell|, \quad (19)$$

Figure 3. Quantum mechanical auto encoder model. To the left an initial state $|\Psi\rangle$ is prepared with training parameters $\vec{\theta}_E$ for the encoding map \mathcal{G} and $\vec{\theta}_D$ for the decoding map \mathcal{G}^\dagger . The input feature \vec{x} is encoded into the input feature map \mathcal{U} and into the input feature encoder \mathcal{M} to the right to produce the state $|\Psi'\rangle$. The model is generalized to a circuit of arbitrary amount of size, depth and compression.

where \mathbb{P}_ℓ is the probability that the bottleneck state collapses to the basis vector $|\ell\rangle$ upon projective measurement. It is given by the equation

$$\mathbb{P}_\ell = \sum_{\ell_c \subseteq I_c} |\phi_{\ell \cup \ell_c}|^2. \quad (20)$$

It is found that the density matrix actually describes a pure quantum state. The deterministic bottleneck operator can therefore be defined as the operator which produce the separated state when applied on a qubit circuit $|\Psi\rangle$.

$$\hat{B}|\Psi\rangle = \sum_{\ell \subseteq I_s - I_c} \sqrt{\mathbb{P}_\ell} |\ell\rangle. \quad (21)$$

This paper adds a hadamard gate to each qubit $|\psi_j\rangle$ that has been measured. So, for each $j \in I_c$ the gate is added. This is to ensure symmetry between the basis states $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$ after internal compression.

The bottleneck equations (16) and (21) imply that a two qubit circuit given by

$$|\Psi\rangle = \phi_\emptyset |\emptyset\rangle + \phi_{\{1\}} |1\rangle + \phi_{\{2\}} |2\rangle + \phi_{\{1,2\}} |1,2\rangle \quad (22)$$

with a single amount of compression would collapse to the state $\frac{\phi_\emptyset |\emptyset\rangle + \phi_{\{1\}} |1\rangle}{\sqrt{|\phi_\emptyset|^2 + |\phi_{\{1\}}|^2}}$, if the second qubit was measured and recorded as collapsing to the basis state $|0\rangle$, corresponding to $\ell_c = \emptyset$. That is non-deterministic compression, but in deterministic compression the second qubit would be measured and *not* recorded. In that

case, the circuit would collapse to the state

$$\sqrt{|\phi_\emptyset|^2 + |\phi_{\{2\}}|^2} |\emptyset\rangle + \sqrt{|\phi_{\{1\}}|^2 + |\phi_{\{1,2\}}|^2} |1\rangle \quad (23)$$

$$(\phi_\emptyset |\emptyset\rangle + \phi_{\{1\}} |1\rangle)(\langle\emptyset| \phi_\emptyset^* + \langle 1| \phi_{\{1\}}^*) \quad (24)$$

$$+ (\phi_{\{2\}} |\emptyset\rangle + \phi_{\{1,2\}} |1\rangle)(\langle\emptyset| \phi_{\{2\}}^* + \langle 1| \phi_{\{1,2\}}^*) \quad (25)$$

$$= (|\phi_\emptyset|^2 + |\phi_{\{2\}}|^2) |\emptyset\rangle \langle\emptyset| + (|\phi_{\{1\}}|^2 + |\phi_{\{1,2\}}|^2) |1\rangle \langle 1| \quad (26)$$

$$+ (\phi_\emptyset^* \phi_{\{1\}} + \phi_{\{2\}}^* \phi_{\{1,2\}}) |1\rangle \langle\emptyset| + (\phi_\emptyset \phi_{\{1\}}^* + \phi_{\{2\}} \phi_{\{1,2\}}^*) |\emptyset\rangle \langle 1| \quad (27)$$

by applying equation (21). The state might also have phase shifts $e^{i\varphi_\emptyset}$ and $e^{i\varphi_{\{1\}}}$ associated with it, but these can not be calculated by this procedure.

3.4. The construction - Defining the QAE model

The formulated quantum mechanical auto encoder model is sketched in figure 3. A qubit circuit $|\Psi\rangle$ is prepared by the following consecutive use of feature maps

$$|\Psi\rangle = \mathcal{G}^\dagger(\vec{\theta}_D) \cdot \hat{B} \cdot \mathcal{G}(\vec{\theta}_E) \cdot \mathcal{U}(\vec{x}) |0\rangle^{\otimes s} \quad (28)$$

The value of $|\Psi\rangle$ can be varied by varying the training parameters $\vec{\theta}_E$ and $\vec{\theta}_D$. This circuit is considered as the auto encoder. Another qubit circuit $|\Psi'\rangle$ is prepared for encoding the input features x_i :

$$|\Psi'\rangle = \mathcal{M}(\vec{x}) |0\rangle^{\otimes s} = [R_y(x_i) H |0\rangle_i]^{\otimes i \in I_s} \quad (29)$$

As a measure of similarity between the prepared qubit circuits, the fidelity measure is calculated. It is given by the equation

$$F = |\langle \Psi(\vec{x}, \vec{\theta}_E, \vec{\theta}_D) | \Psi(\vec{x}) \rangle|^2 \quad (30)$$

Suppose we have a training set of input samples $S_n = \{\vec{x}_1, \vec{x}_2, \dots, \vec{x}_n\}$. Similar to (Abbas et al., pg. 5), we define the empirical risk $R_n(\vec{\theta}_E, \vec{\theta}_D)$ as the mean of the log-fidelity.

$$R_n(\vec{\theta}_E, \vec{\theta}_D) = -\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \log F(\vec{x}_i, \vec{\theta}_E, \vec{\theta}_D) \quad (31)$$

The empirical risk is the loss function that must be minimized by tuning the values of the training parameters. Minimizing the loss function will make the auto encoder circuit output align as closely as possible to the separable input feature encoding map. From there, the input feature vector can be reconstructed by the scheme explained in section 3.2.

3.5. The trainability of a single qubit circuit QAE model

The single qubit circuit quantum mechanical auto encoder model with no bottleneck has a guaranteed large range of the fidelity measure. The fidelity measure of the system is given by

$$\begin{aligned} F &= |\langle 0 | H^\dagger R_y(-x) R_y(\theta_D) R_y(\theta_E) R_z(x) H | 0 \rangle|^2 \\ &= \frac{1}{2} + \sin \phi \cos \phi \cos x \end{aligned} \quad (32)$$

The fidelity has been calculated in the last equation (32), where $\phi = \theta_D + \theta_D - x + \frac{\pi}{4}$. By differentiating with respect to the sum of the training parameters it is found that the fidelity is maximal, when $\theta_D + \theta_E = x$. Another solution requires $\cos x = 0$, but that would require a feature x outside the range of normalization $[0; 1]$, so this solution is discarded. At the point $x = \theta_D + \theta_E$ the fidelity equals

$$F_{\max}(x) = \frac{1}{2}(1 + \cos x) \quad (33)$$

For a normalized input feature x , the maximal fidelity takes on the values in the interval $F_{\max} \in [0.77; 1]$. The relatively large range of the maximal fidelity gives merit for testing the extended QAE model.

4. Methods of numerical optimization

The PSO class in the QAE package was inspired by the pseudocode implemented in (Engelbrecht, pg. 291). Particle swarm optimization starts by creating a sample set of particles¹ $\{p_i\}$. Each particle has a vector \vec{r}_i associated with it, describing a current position in euclidian space. At each time-iteration, the particles are accelerated with one force pointing towards the best *personal* position \vec{y}_i and one towards the *best global* position \hat{y} . The velocity vectors \vec{v}_i of each particle p_i are updated by the following equation (Engelbrecht, pg. 290):

$$\Delta \vec{v}_i = c_1 r_1 (\vec{y}_i - \vec{r}_i) + c_2 r_2 (\hat{y} - \vec{r}_i), \quad (34)$$

for each consecutive timesteps. The values r_1 and r_2 are pseudo-randomly generated uniformly on the interval $[-\pi, \pi]$, and c_1 and c_2 are positive optimization constants which determine the proportional acceleration towards the personal or global best particle position. We define the best position as a maximum of the fidelity measure $F(\vec{\theta})$ with respect to a set of training parameters $\vec{r} = \vec{\theta}$. The empirical risk function $R_n(\vec{\theta})$ should be optimized to be minimal. Each timestep is chosen to be one time unit apart $\Delta t = 1$, so that each particle position is updated likewise $\vec{r}_i \mapsto \vec{r}_i + \Delta \vec{v}_i$. The new valued positions are compared for each iteration to update the personal and global best positions according to the optimization scheme.

Particle swarm optimization is suitable for finding extrema that do not overfit the autoencoder. To further optimize the auto encoder from a PSO-found point, Euler's method is applied. The method comes from a first order Taylor expansion. We apply the first order Taylor expansion on a differentiable function f of two neighboring points $\vec{\theta}$ and $\vec{\theta}' = \vec{\theta} + \Delta \vec{\theta}$. These points are distanced by a vector $\Delta \vec{\theta}$. The Taylor expansion reads:

$$f(\vec{\theta}') \approx f(\vec{\theta}) + \left. \frac{\partial f}{\partial \vec{\theta}'} \right|_{\vec{\theta}'=\vec{\theta}} \cdot \Delta \vec{\theta}. \quad (35)$$

If the points are sufficiently close, we can approximate $\left. \frac{\partial f}{\partial \vec{\theta}'} \right|_{\vec{\theta}'=\vec{\theta}}$ by the true gradient $\frac{\partial f}{\partial \vec{\theta}} =$

¹ Note that the "particle" analogy should not be confused with physical particles, but merely point-like particles of zero dimension in euclidian space

Figure 4. Iris data set histogram plot. The dataset consists of 4-tuples (x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4) where each value in the tuple corresponds to a feature of an Iris flower. There are three types of Iris flowers, namely; Setosa (blue), Versicolor (orange) and Virginia (not depicted). To the right is a QAE model’s reconstruction of the Iris-data set, for a model of depth four and compression one. The reconstructions are marked by the color of the same Iris category as it was prior to reconstruction.

$\nabla_{\vec{\theta}} f$. From the above equation, it is found that the direction of steepest ascend is given, when the vector difference $\Delta\vec{\theta}$ is parallel to the gradient. That is $\Delta\vec{\theta} = \eta \cdot \nabla_{\vec{\theta}} f$ for a constant $\eta \in \mathbb{R}$. The numerical size of η is proportional to the distance between the two neighboring points. η is positive for a gradient ascend and negative for a gradient descend. Gradient ascend is thus formally defined by the recursive mapping:

$$\vec{\theta} \mapsto \vec{\theta} + \eta \frac{\partial f}{\partial \vec{\theta}}. \quad (36)$$

5. Results

5.1. Training set and Qualitative Replication

The same data set used by [Abbas et al.] was primarily used to develop the QAE model of this paper. The data set is called "Iris" and is the top rated data set on its creators website; Dua and Casey. The data set consists of 50 data features for each of the three types of Iris flowers.

In analysing the input replication of the QAE model, this paper developed an input feature encoder \mathcal{M} . The encoder is designed to be invertible, meaning it is possible to

construct the input feature vector \vec{x} from the encoder output $\mathcal{M}(\vec{x})|0\rangle^{\otimes s}$. Because of this approach we are able to qualitatively compare the reconstructed input of the autoencoder to the real input as seen in figure 4.

5.2. Training and Mean Convergence

The QAE model is trained on the Iris data set, specifically with models of depth 4 - compression zero, one or two. The training process for each amount of compression is plotted in figure 5. The fidelity optimization is done by a hundred iterations of particle swarm optimization and fifty iterations of gradient descend on the empirical risk equation (31).

In analysing the reconstructed inputs in figure 4 and appendix G, it is noticed how the distributions seem to align well in the general area, on which the real distributions are located. Furthermore, the autoencoder is occasionally even able to distinguish the two different categories of Iris flowers, by there being an empty gap in between the reconstructed distributions. Even when there is overlap, there are definite distinguishable peaks. As well as learning a shape of the sample distributions, the autoencoder trains to place

Figure 5. Particle swarm optimization on a depth 4 - compression 0 (left) and 1 (right) QAE model. 40 particles moving for 100 iterations to find a minimum value of the empirical risk R_n in the training parameter space $\vec{\theta} \in \mathbb{R}^{2s(d+1)}$. Afterwards the fidelity is maximized with gradient ascend for 50 iterations. The empirical risk is referred to as the loss score and given by equation (31). It is defined as the negative mean of the log-fidelity.

Figure 6. The convergence of the reconstructed distribution means. This depiction shows 100 iterations particle swarm optimization, followed by 50 iterations of gradient ascend. The distributions are separated into their distinct categories, separated by flower types (Setosa and Versicolour) and attributes (Petal length, Sepal width, etc.). The dotted lines represent the real mean values, drawn from the Iris data set, while the solid lines show the mean of the QAE reconstructed samples. A proposed division of the emergent learning processes is given at the bottom of this figure. At the bottom is a table of the empirical mean and variance of the eigenvalue distributions along with the maximal eigenvalues encountered for each spectra.

them in the same general area, expressed by the mean of the sample distributions. To get a better understanding of the training process, the evolution of each distribution's mean value of a depth four and compression one QAE

model has been plotted in figure 6.

5.3. Capacity Analysis

The empirical Fisher information matrix $\tilde{\mathbb{F}}$ can be computed by equation 1 in (Abbas et al., pg.

Figure 7. Fisher information spectra of a depth 4 - compression 0, 1 and 2 QAE model. The eigenvectors \vec{v} of the Fisher information matrix $\tilde{\mathbb{F}}$ are the vectors that only scale when applying the matrix operation: $\tilde{\mathbb{F}}\vec{v} = \lambda\vec{v}$. The eigenvalues λ are calculated numerically for each sampled Fisher matrix. For each spectra in this figure, a hundred Fisher matrices are generated by a hundred uniformly generated training parameters $\vec{\theta} \in [-1; 1]^{2s(d+1)}$, for a size $s = 4$ and depth $d = 4$ QAE model. A total of 40 trainable parameters. The values of the input vectors \vec{x} are generated from a standard normal distribution centered at $\mu_x = 0$ with a standard deviation of $\sigma_x = 1$. For each of the generated training parameters, 100 priorly sampled input vectors $\vec{x} \in \mathbb{R}^s$ are generated to compute each Fisher matrix with equation (37). The spectra are simulated for a QAE model with zero, one and two degrees of compression. The bar charts are normalized so that the sum of bar frequencies for a given plot is 1.

4). The gradient of the log-fidelity measure is noted as $\vec{g}_i(\vec{\theta}) = \nabla_{\vec{\theta}} \log F(\vec{x}_i, \vec{\theta})$. Given a vector of training parameters $\vec{\theta}$, the corresponding empirical Fisher matrix can be computed by the mean of the outer product of the gradient log-fidelity \vec{g}_i .

$$\tilde{\mathbb{F}}(\vec{\theta}) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \vec{g}_i(\vec{\theta}) \vec{g}_i(\vec{\theta})^T \quad (37)$$

The eigenvalues of $\tilde{\mathbb{F}}$ are important in analysing the trainability of the neural network. A lot of eigenvalues close to zero correspond to a statistical model with many Barren plateaus. (Abbas et al., pg. 7).

It is apparent in figure 7 that higher compression leads to more frequent eigenvalues close to zero. Even though, compression can yield better fidelity in training, it is found that compression leads to a more degenerate Fisher spectrum, which thereby leads to a larger prob-

ability of encountering a Barren plateau (Abbas et al., pg. 8). The article by [Karakida et al.] studies the Fisher spectrum of a classical autoencoder of varying size. This study can compare the mean, variance, and maximal value to their results for an auto encoder of size four with the table in figure 7. Their mean are considerable less than the values produced by the QAE model by at least three orders of magnitude. The comparatively large eigenvalues of the QAE model might make it more favorable in relation to gradient optimization. However, this has not been tested for networks of increasing size.

6. Discussion

6.1. Problem of differentiating classes of data
The developed auto encoder has trouble differentiating distributions of different classes. It often optimizes to the mean of the two data classes, or it may switch the position of the distributions. The model has not been tested

on more than two types of data classes and increasing the types might make differentiating them more difficult for the model. It should be noted that the model consistently manages to separate the peaks of the distributions but the gaussian tails often overlap. Some incentive would be needed to separate distributions of different classes and could perhaps be done by adding a bias to the loss function. In the article by [Gianani et al.], the loss function is suppressed by adding a fidelity term $\log |\langle a|b \rangle|$ which discriminates against having the output state vectors of two different classes a and b be closely aligned. This term would have to be weighted properly to not undermine the $-\log |\langle a|a' \rangle|$ and $-\log |\langle b|b' \rangle|$ terms which minimize the reconstruction loss. This point is especially important for training sets with an increasing number of data classes.

6.2. The necessity of an entangling input feature map

Merely having the initial feature map \mathcal{U}_I or the input feature encoder \mathcal{M} at the start of the auto encoder circuit in figure 3, will cause the reconstructed input to overfit. For these circuits, it will often reconstruct all feature samples to a single point which lies at the mean of the sampled distributions. Therefore, it seems necessary for the whole entangling input feature map \mathcal{U} to be included as it counteracts this behaviour as it gives width to the reconstructed distributions.

6.3. Applications

Autoencoders are effective in many areas of data and computer science such as denoising data (Bank et al., pg. 4). In figure 8 this effect is demonstrated by the QAE model.

The developed QAE model could be extended to function as a variational auto encoder. Suppose the auto encoder has been trained on a set of data features. The state in the middle of the bottleneck after compression and before restoration is called the latent state $|\Psi_{I_c}\rangle$, which exists in a lower dimensional $s - c$ latent state space. A priorly sampled latent state variable $|z\rangle$ may be entangled with the circuit by computing their tensor product

Figure 8. The effect of data denoising on a QAE model with compression one. Gaussian noise has been added to the Iris data set and the resulting input has been fed into the QAE model. The reconstructions has the property of having a more well-defined boundary compared to the noisy input.

$|\Psi_{I_c}\rangle \otimes |z\rangle$ (Romero et al., pg. 8). By optimizing DVAE log-likelihood measure (Gircha et al., pg. 1), the decoding map \mathcal{G}^\dagger could function as a generator of data given a latent state variable $|z\rangle$. However, to make the variational auto encoder functional on this QAE model, it will most likely require that the model is improved to better differentiate between data of different classes as discussed in section 6.1.

7. Conclusion

In this paper, we have constructed a qubit circuit (figure 3) which mimics the reconstruction properties of a classical auto encoder model. This is done by applying the formulated feature maps \mathcal{U} and \mathcal{G} developed by [Abbas et al.] into a encoding - decoding scheme. Internal compression has been studied according to the formulation by [Romero et al.] and a deterministic bottleneck operator \hat{B} has been derived in equation (21) to simulate this event. When applying an input feature encoder $\mathcal{M}(\vec{x})$ to the circuit we reach a large fidelity measure when comparing the auto encoder output state to the encoder's output state. By the construction of \mathcal{M} , it is possible to reconstruct the input vector from a trained a QAE model. The model has been trained on the Iris data set for a varying amount of internal compression. For each, capacity analysis is performed by computing the eigenvalues of a number of sampled Fisher matrices. The Fisher spectrum is relatively non-degenerate with many large eigenvalues above 0, so optimizing a quantum auto

encoder model seems more efficient to a classical model [Karakida et al.].

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8. Appendix

8.1. Appendix A: Input reconstruction spectrogram

Figure 9. Spectrogram for three amounts of internal compression on a depth four QAE model. Data pairs (x, y) has been plotted on each square. The pair consists of a feature x from the Iris data set and a reconstructed feature y by the QAE model. The diagonal squares for example represent the direct mapping of a feature to its reconstruction. The distributions in these squares are expected to lay close to their diagonal for a good reconstruction. Areas of densely populated points are colored yellow, while areas with no points are colored dark blue. The spectrogram bearing the most resemblance to the (x, x) plot (top - left) is the depth four compression one plot (top-right). It is especially noticeable, that the autoencoder typically optimises to the mean of the two distinct distributions, in the depth four compression two plot (lower-right).

8.2. Appendix G: Training session - Random compression

The training session of this section is coded using deterministic compression. The state of the qubit circuit after has been derived in equation (21). The left graph depict the reconstructed input after particale swarm optimization, and the right graph depict it after further gradiant ascend.

Depth 4 QAEM reconstructed input, with zero qubit compression:

Depth 4 QAEM reconstructed input, with single qubit compression:

Depth 4 QAEM reconstructed input, with double qubit compression:

8.3. Appendix C: Relational diagram of code classes of the developed QAE python package

Figure 10. Relational scheme of the developed QAE python package. In all, 13 distinct classes were developed. Arrows point from a class to a box of some of its class methods. Most of the implemented methods are of simple types e.g. accessor or mutator methods. The proceeding arrows are directed at another class where these methods are accessed. All class methods takes a parameter self as a reference to an object instance of the class. The self-referencing parameter is implicit in the relational scheme. The feature maps in the QAE model is simulated with the QMaps class that uses methods from the QubitCircuit class provided by the QuTiP package [Johansson et al.].